

Temperature-sensing receptor-mediated thermocrine signaling between biotic and abiotic components

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Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine signaling, and water-based aquacrine signaling. Additionally, they signal via temperature, compete by regulating temperature, and sense temperature released by abiotic components. However, to the best of my knowledge, there are no specific unifying scientific terms to describe temperature-mediated organismal communication or the sensing of temperature from abiotic components. I propose thermocrine signaling to include not only thermal radiation-based communication between organisms but also between abiotic components and organisms. The sensing of temperature can occur via both membranal and non-membranal receptors, including temperature-sensing proteins with various additional domains such as protease, kinase, guanylate cyclase, transcription factor, etc or temperature-sensing riboreceptors. Temperature plays an essential role in the mobility of both nucleic acid-based and protein-based gasoreceptors, metalloceptors, aquareceptors and their signaling machinery. Therefore, tightly regulated sensing of temperature becomes a fundamental requirement for gasocrine- and metallochrine-based organismal communication. This regulation is crucial for sustaining both animal and plant life.